

APHORISM, ITS ORIGIN AND SIGNIFICANCE IN OUR SOCIAL LIFE

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Abstract: This article analyzes in detail the etymology of the term aphorism and theoretical views on the problem. The first cases of using this term in science, aphorisms on various topics and their significance in our lives are highlighted.

Keywords: aphorism, Heraclitus, Hippocrates, Pascal, Goethe, Lichtenberg, , axiom, Oxford Book of Aphorisms.

It is obvious that the language is changing significantly right before our eyes. There are many opinions of scientists about the good and bad sides of this phenomenon. Currently, linguistics is studying in depth the problems of non-standard speech, exploring its features and characteristics due to the fact that in modern language there is a wide spread of aphorisms in social networks.

In our dynamic era with its high pace of life and a huge amount of literary and information products, the most capacious genre of literature - aphoristics - is in great demand. Elements of aphoristic thinking allow us to single out something very essential for knowledge in the sea of information, to determine our personal position. Aphoristic expression generalizes and typifies the diverse manifestations of personal and social life, and also firmly exists in communication as its organic part, as a capacious and concentrated form of artistic reflection of reality and expression of the attitude of language to it.

Aphorisms are the subject of research of linguists, literary scholars, historians, philosophers. However, despite the ancient origin of aphoristics, as well as the wide use of aphorisms in speech, the phenomenon of aphorism has not yet been fully studied. This is confirmed by the very definition of the concept of "aphorism", which is interpreted by linguists in different ways. A vast field for discussion is the forms of aphorisms, their structural and semantic features. These provisions confirm the relevance of our study.

The purpose of this work is to identify and describe the structural and semantic features of English-language aphorisms, using the aphorisms of the authors we have selected as an example.

The relevance of this study is determined by the need to analyze the influence of social networks on the subject of semantics and stylistics of English aphorisms using social networks as an example. The Internet, as is known, is currently the most global means of transmitting information among

young people. It quickly disseminates information about current events both within the country and around the world, broadens the horizons of young people. In addition, when transmitting information, social networks influence the audience of their readers, shape their worldview, perception, behavior and assessment of the world around them.

The object of the study is English aphorisms using social networks as an example.

The subject is the semantic and stylistic analysis of English aphorisms in social networks.

In order to characterize aphorism more fully, let us consider several of the most illustrative definitions.

"An aphorism is a short and expressive saying" (Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language, 1935).

"Aphorism is a short clever saying that is intended to express a general truth" (<http://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/aphorism>).

"Aphorism is a terse saying embodying a general truth, or astute observation" (<http://www.dictionary.com/browse/aphorism>).

"Aphorism is a concise expression of doctrine or principle or any generally accepted truth conveyed in a pithy, memorable statement" (<https://www.britannica.com/art/aphorism>).

"Aphorism – 1. A pithy observation which contains a general truth; 2. A concise statement of a scientific principle, typically by a classical author»" (<https://en.oxforddictionaries.com/definition/aphorism>).

From the above definitions, we can highlight several distinctive properties of an aphorism, such as: brevity, paradoxicality, originality, memorability, and, often, the presence of an author. Considering all of the above properties, let's make our own definition of an aphorism.

"An aphorism is an original, complete thought, expressed in a short, memorable form, reflecting well-known truths or a generalized, deep thought of the author."

An aphorism is characterized by the fullness and completeness of the semantic content, brevity and precision of verbal expression, aphorisms are often called everyday wisdom. Often, an aphorism does not cause contradictions in the reader, it only reminds of simple truths that a person neglects. Aphoristics widely use puns, logical shifts, manifested in the opposition of similar concepts and identifications of opposites; unexpectedness is achieved by destroying the associations fixed behind words.

Aphorism as a literary genre is attractive to the reader due to the novelty and unexpectedness of the content, the polish of the form. It is attractive both in a separate form and in the context of a speech, article or work of art. Aphorisms created specifically as aphorisms predominate in numerous collections of aphorisms or on websites on the Internet. Not so numerous are catchphrases and quotations created in the context of works or speeches of authors. The most prominent representatives of aphorism as an independent genre are: F. de La Rochefoucauld, N. Chamfort, B. Pascal, I.V. Goethe, S.E. Lets, and others. Many aphorisms are quotations from works; For example, most of Oscar Wilde's aphorisms are lines from his plays.

The modern concept of an aphorism is not exhaustive, since it does not take into account its artistic aspect. In this regard, we can give a final definition of an aphorism in the following words: an aphorism is a deep, striving for truth and obtained by generalization, a complete thought of a certain author in an extremely brief, polished and highly artistic form. At this stage of the study, the aphorisms of the sample were analyzed from the point of view of the semantics of their general meaning, i.e. the meaning of the aphorism as a whole. Usually, the subject of aphorisms is aimed at "eternal questions": about truth and justice, life and death, war and peace, happiness and unhappiness, about the state structure, etc. It reflects all facets of human individuality and human society.

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